

CHOICE OF IMMOBILIZATION TACTICS FOR MANDIBULAR FRACTURES IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC GENERALIZED PERIODONTITIS

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Relevance

Objective: to justify the choice of an optimal way of immobilization of the fragments in patients with mandibular fractures and chronic generalized periodontitis of a severe degree. **Materials and methods.** 70 patients with mandibular fractures in combination with chronic generalized periodontitis, who were subject to immobilization of the mandible in different ways, were examined. The patients underwent a routine clinical examination and study of cytokines, as well as C-terminal telopeptides of the contents of periodontal pockets. **Results.** It was revealed that in the dynamics of orthodontic treatment the patients showed the progression of inflammatory and destructive processes. When the mandible was immobilized using intermaxillary fixation on titanium screws and during surgical treatment, the inflammatory phenomena at the level of periodontal pockets were relieved. **Conclusion.** Given the lower number of purulent-inflammatory complications in mandibular fractures in the group of patients who used interdental fixation with titanium screws, this method is the most optimal.

Introduction. Mandible fractures are common pathology in the work of a dental surgeon. According to different authors, their frequency is 72–85% of all fractures

of the facial skeleton [1]. The course of the post-traumatic period of mandible fractures is affected by various factors, including periodontal diseases [2, 3]. A direct strong correlation between the frequency of purulent-inflammatory complications in mandible fractures and the severity of periodontal disease has been proven [4]. The negative effect of double jaw dental splints on periodontal tissues has been studied.

Alternative to orthodontic treatment are surgical methods, however they lead to the development of a greater number of inflammatory complications [5, 6, 7].

Therefore, patients with mandible fractures and severe periodontitis require a special approach in the choice of the method of immobilization of fragments, and the study of the impact of various methods of immobilization of mandible fragments on periodontal tissues and on the development of fracture complications in patients with chronic generalized periodontitis of a severe degree is a topical problem of dentistry.

Objective: Substantiate the choice of the optimal method for immobilization of fragments in patients with mandible fractures in chronic generalized periodontitis of severe severity.

Material and methods. 70 patients with lower jaw fractures were under the observation in the Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center of traumatology and orthopedics of the Samarkand branch, in the Department of maxillofacial surgery, who, upon admission for inpatient treatment, were diagnosed with chronic generalized periodontitis of severe severity. All examined patients were divided into three groups: Group 1 consisted of 30 patients, in the treatment of who were used immobilization of the lower jaw with bimaxillary tooth splints, group II - 20 patients who underwent osteosynthesis surgery without additional intermaxillary fixation, group III - 20 patients, for immobilization of the lower jaw which were used structures, not fixed on the dental arches (intermaxillary fixation on titanium screws).

The comparison was made with the indicators of the control group, which consisted of 20 volunteers, practically healthy people. The program of examination of patients included identification of complaints, collection of anamnesis, external examination of the maxillofacial region, X-ray examination of the dentoalveolar system. To study the periodontal tissues and the hygienic state of the oral cavity, the hygienic and periodontal indices were used. Of the laboratory research methods, for assessing the state of the periodontal tissues, a study of the level of cytokines IL-17, IL-18, reflecting the metabolism of bone tissue in the contents of periodontal pockets by the solid-phase enzyme immunoassay method was used. A study of the level of s-terminal telopeptides of the contents of periodontal pockets was carried out with the Nordic Bioscience Diagnostics A / S Serum CrossLaps ELISA test system. The study was carried out on the day of admission of patients for inpatient treatment, on the 9-10th day of treatment and on the 28-30th day of treatment.

Results. Upon admission of patients with mandibular fractures in combination with chronic generalized periodontitis for inpatient treatment, all patients that we examined had poor oral hygiene, a high value of the hygiene index (HI), which averaged 2.25, the values of the periodontal index (PI) corresponded to a severe degree of periodontitis, the papillary-marginal-alveolar (PMA) index - to a moderate degree of gingivitis. Further studies have shown that in patients of group I, the hygienic state of the oral cavity worsens significantly due to the formation of dental plaque mainly from the oral side of the teeth.

At the time of splint removal, in 55% of cases an increase in the depth of periodontal pockets by 1 mm was noted, an increase in HI values by 22% and PMA index by 47%, no reliable changes in PI were revealed. The percentage of purulent-inflammatory complications of fractures in this group was 25%, and their transition to a chronic form was 15%. In group II of patients who used the surgical method of treatment, the state of oral hygiene on the 30th day of treatment improved, on

average, the HI values corresponded to satisfactory oral hygiene. The values of the periodontal indices did not change significantly. No changes in the depth of periodontal pockets were revealed. An important fact is that the proportion of purulent-inflammatory complications in this group was high and amounted to 33.3%, and the transition to a chronic form was noted in 26.6% of cases.

In the 3rd group of patients, where the intermaxillary fixation with titanium screws was used for fragments immobilization, there was slight worsening of oral cavity hygiene related to dental plaque on the oral side of the teeth. Changes in depth of periodontal pockets weren't identified, the values of hygiene and periodontal indexes increased slightly. The percentage of inflammatory complications during fracture healing in this group made only 13%, while the transition to chronic form made 6%. The IL-18 level in the contents of periodontal pockets of patients in the examined groups was significantly increased in the first days after the injury as compared to the control group against the background of reduced IL-17 level, which is probably the reflection of acute generalized periodontitis, as well as the primary response of the organism to the trauma characterized by the processes of destruction of the cells and structures composing the bone, acute inflammatory reaction to the tissue damage.

When comparing the cytokine level in all three groups of patients in dynamics, we identified substantial differences. The IL-18 level in the dental pocket content of patients in the 1st group increased in dynamics of the treatment, whereas the IL-17 level declined. The indicated changes in the presence of mandible fracture consolidation indicate the progression of destructive processes at the periodontal tissue level. In the groups of patients, where the surgical method of treatment was used as well as the mandible immobilization using the intermaxillary fixation with titanium screws, there was a tendency towards normalization of the studied cytokine level by the 28-30th day, indicating the deceleration of bone tissue destruction

processes at the periodontal tissue level. In the patients with lower jaw fractures associated with chronic periodontitis, there was an increased level of c-terminal telopeptides identified upon the hospitalization, as compared to the control group, by 2.5 times on average (up to 0.55 ng/ml), which is caused by the progression of periodontal bone tissue destruction as well as by the primary response to the trauma characterized by the processes of destruction of the cells and structures forming the bone. However, the indicators in all the three groups were not significant. Significant differences were identified during the treatment. For example, on the 28-30th day of treatment in the 1st group of patients, the c-terminal telopeptides level indicator in the periodontal pocket contents increased by 70% as compared to the hospitalization data (on average, it was 0.94 ng/ml) and exceeded the control group indicator more than three times. The c-terminal telopeptides level in the 2nd and 3rd groups of patients approached the control group level by the 28-30th day of treatment; their indicators declined to 0.35 ng/ml on average. The data obtained indicate the decreased activity of bone resorption at the periodontal tissue level in the patients of the 2nd and 3rd groups as well as the increased destructive processes at the periodontal tissue level in the 1st group of patients upon the removal of dental splints despite the formation of primary bone callus in most of the studied patients of the given group.

Discussion. Clinical and laboratory examination of patients with mandibular fractures combined with chronic periodontitis in dynamics of orthopedic treatment revealed the progression of inflammatory-destructive processes, the transition of chronic inflammation into the acute stage with the prevalence of degenerative changes in the periodontal pockets. When the mandible is immobilized using the intermaxillary fixation with titanium screws, inflammatory manifestations at the periodontal pocket level in patients are relieved by the 28-30th day of treatment. In surgical treatment, osteosynthesis with titanium mini-plates without intermaxillary fixation, there is also a relief of inflammation in periodontal tissues. However,

considering the smaller number of purulent-inflammatory complications of fractures in the group of patients where the intermaxillary fixation with titanium screws was used, its use is more appropriate in the treatment of patients with mandibular fractures combined with chronic periodontitis.

Conclusion. Based on our research, we developed an algorithm for choosing the method of immobilization of fragments in patients with chronic generalized periodontitis during mandibular fractures. In patients with mandibular fractures and severe chronic generalized periodontitis, it is necessary to: 1) exclude the use of double jaw dental splints; 2) if the mandibular fracture is without displacement of fragments or with displacement eliminated by manual reposition, the intermaxillary fixation with titanium screws is indicated; 3) if the mandible fracture is with displacement of fragments not eliminated by manual reposition, the osteosynthesis surgery without intermaxillary fixation is indicated. **Literature:**

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